

ULTRASTRUCTURAL AND MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF THE STOMATOPOD DACTYL CLUB EXOCUTICLE

Nicholas A. Yaraghi¹, Lessa Grunenfelder^{2,3}, Nicolás-Guarín Zapata⁴, Nobphadon Suksangpanya⁴, Steven Herrera¹, Christopher Salinas³, Garrett Milliron⁵, Isaias Gallana⁴, Kenneth Evans-Lutterodt⁶, Elaine DiMasi⁶, Steven Nutt², Pablo Zavattieri⁴, David Kisailus³

¹Materials Science and Engineering, University of California, Riverside
Riverside, CA, United States

Emails: nyara001@ucr.edu, sherr006@ucr.edu, webpage: <http://www.mse.ucr.edu/>

²Chemical Engineering and Materials Science, University of Southern California
Los Angeles, CA, United States

Emails: grunenfe@usc.edu, nutt@usc.edu, webpage: <http://chems.usc.edu/>

³Chemical and Environmental Engineering, University of California, Riverside
Riverside, CA, United States

Emails: chris.salinas@gmail.com, david@engr.ucr.edu, webpage: <http://www.cee.ucr.edu/>

⁴Civil Engineering, Purdue University
West Lafayette, IN, United States

Emails: nicoguarin@gmail.com, nsuksang@purdue.edu, gallanaisaias@gmail.com,
zavattie@purdue.edu, webpage: <https://engineering.purdue.edu/CE>

⁵Max Planck Institute for Colloids and Interfaces
Potsdam, Germany

Email: gradies@gmail.com, webpage: <http://www.mpikg.mpg.de/en>

⁶Synchrotron Light Source Department, Brookhaven National Lab
Upton, NY, United States

Emails: dimasi@bnl.gov, kenne@bnl.gov, webpage: <http://www.bnl.gov/ps/>

Keywords: Dactyl club, Impact region, Bouligand, Herringbone, Nanoindentation

ABSTRACT

High performance structural materials require a combination of adequate strength and toughness. Moreover, ongoing demands for economical and environmentally friendly solutions require new classes of materials that are durable, lightweight, and efficiently produced. Nature has long demonstrated the ability to synthesize composite materials under relatively mild conditions that exhibit a high degree of sophistication and impressive mechanical properties. These materials have been carefully crafted through evolutionary pressures to fulfill specific functions such as weapons for hunting and defense. One example of this is the raptorial appendage (dactyl club) of the stomatopod, *Odontodactylus scyllarus*, a marine crustacean. This species employs its dactyl clubs to aggressively hunt and smash through the mechanically tough exteriors of its prey, which include mollusks, crabs, and other hard-shelled organisms. The dactyl club is capable of enduring thousands of repetitive high-energy strikes and cavitation at the impact surface without catastrophically failing. Here, we investigate the ultrastructural and mechanical features of the dactyl club exocuticle. We identify domains consisting of an oriented crystalline hydroxyapatite mineral phase, which exhibits rod-like and particle morphology. Additionally, this mineral phase is templated by an underlying organic scaffold composed of a unique arrangement of chitin fibrils. This ultrastructure results in a stiff and hard outer layer for delivering damaging blows and protecting the club's soft interior. These findings as well as further investigation of the growth mechanisms of the dactyl club will provide insights into the formation of composite materials that exhibit well-defined morphology and exceptional impact resistance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nature's ability to fabricate hierarchical structures while controlling the multi-scale organization of organic and inorganic components has resulted in a diversity of materials that exhibit a wide range of mechanical properties and fulfill numerous functions [1,2]. One such structure is the hammer-like raptorial appendage (dactyl club) of the stomatopod (marine crustacean), *Odontodactylus scyllarus*. This species employs its dactyl clubs to aggressively hunt and strike its prey, which include mollusks, crabs, and other highly mineralized organisms, with tremendous force and speed [3]. The dactyl club is capable of breaking through the mechanically tough exteriors of its prey while enduring thousands of repetitive high-energy strikes and cavitation at the impact surface without catastrophically failing [3].

The stomatopod dactyl club is a multi-regional composite material that contains an organic phase composed of chitinous fibers and an inorganic phase composed of amorphous and crystalline mineral [4]. The interior of the club, which can be divided into the periodic and striated regions, features chitinous fibers arranged in helicoidal (Bouligand) and sheet-like arrangements respectively. These regions contain amorphous calcium carbonate and calcium phosphate. In addition, the club features a stiff and hard outer region that contains a highly oriented crystalline apatitic mineral phase. Much of the success of this material in resisting catastrophic failure has been attributed to the periodic region, which has been identified as the primary-energy absorbing layer. However, details concerning the micro and nano-architecture of the hard and stiff crystalline outer impact region have not yet received full attention. This region is the first site of impact and must be able to withstand incredibly high compressive stresses from impact as well as cavitation without failing, thus warranting further examination. Here, we interrogate the micro and nano-structural features and mechanical properties of the impact region in order to ascertain the functional role of this region and its contribution to the overarching success of this impact-resistant and damage-tolerant natural composite material.

2. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

2.1 Micro-structural features and domains

In order to understand the functional role of the impact region and its contribution to the overall system, the micro-scale architecture of the impact region was initially examined. Optical microscopy of a polished cross-section along the sagittal plane highlights the multi-regional nature of stomatopod dactyl club, revealing the impact and periodic regions (Figure 1C). Higher magnification dark-field imaging shows that the impact region can be divided into two distinct subdomains: the bulk, which comprises the majority in thickness of the impact region (typically 300 to 500 μm) and a thin surface layer, which is approximately 60 to 80 μm in thickness (Figure 1D). We term this outermost layer the impact surface in conjunction with observations previously made by Weaver et al [4]. Figure 1D also highlights the abrupt interfaces separating the bulk of the impact region and the impact surface as well as the impact and periodic regions. A most interesting observation comes from the examination of the impact region using differential interference contrast (DIC) imaging, which reveals a well defined and highly ordered herringbone pattern within the bulk (Figure 1E). Synchrotron x-ray diffraction studies of the impact region previously showed that the apatite crystallites have a preferred orientation with the (002) planes aligned parallel to the club surface [4]. However, the contrast observed in Figure 1E is suggestive of a more sophisticated texturing scheme of the apatitic mineral phase than was previously described [4]. Although these striations are most evident within the bulk of the impact region, the herringbone pattern also appears to continue into the impact surface region, possibly an indication of a structural gradient across the bulk-impact surface interface. Moreover, the herringbone pattern from Figure 1E is faintly visible within the dark-field image in Figure 1D, suggesting that it originates not only from crystallographic texturing but possibly also a well-defined microstructure.

Figure 1. Stomatopod dactyl club overview and optical microscopy. (A) Anterior of *O. scyllarus* with dactyl segment circled in yellow. (B) Dactyl club separated from the raptorial appendage. Yellow box denotes the sagittal plane of section. (C) Low magnification dark-field micrograph of a polished sagittal section as denoted in (B). (D,E) Higher magnification (D) dark-field and (E) differential interference contrast micrographs of region marked in (C) highlighting the impact surface, bulk impact, and periodic regions.

Additional analysis of polished cross-sections of the club under DIC mode (data not shown here) shows a gradual transition from a laminated appearance (characteristic of the Bouligand structure) within the periodic region to a wavy one at the interface between the periodic and impact regions. A well-defined herringbone pattern is then observed once we transition into the bulk of the impact region.

From the optical micrographs, the herringbone pattern can be assumed to be analogous to a triangular waveform. We observe that each herringbone subunit within the bulk of the impact region has an identical wavelength equal to approximately $45\ \mu\text{m}$. However, the amplitude of these units is graded in the radial direction with a minimum amplitude of approximately $70\ \mu\text{m}$ observed at the impact-periodic region interface and a maximum amplitude of approximately $100\ \mu\text{m}$ located at the interface between the bulk impact region and impact surface. Interestingly, the amplitude appears to have a global minimum of approximately $50\ \mu\text{m}$ located within the impact surface region.

The dactyl club was subsequently mechanically fractured along the sagittal plane and examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to interrogate the microstructural features. Figure 2A shows a low magnification micrograph of the resulting fractured surface. Closer inspection at the impact-periodic region interface shows the contrasting microstructures between the periodic and impact regions. The fractured surface of the periodic region shows a laminated microstructure characteristic of a Bouligand arrangement of mineralized chitin fibers. This helicoidal arrangement of fibers is a common design found in most arthropod cuticles [6-8]. Subsequent examination of the bulk of the impact region (Figure 2B) from the region denoted in Figure 2A reveals the herringbone pattern, which correlates with optical observations made in Figure 1D. Higher magnification imaging of the bulk of the impact region reveals what appears to be a modified Bouligand structure. Fibers continue to rotate in the plane of the page; however, individual periods of rotation appear to be compacted in the azimuthal direction to form the herringbone pattern (Figure 2C). Dashed lines indicate the transitional zones from mineralized fibers oriented in the plane of fractured and out of the plane of

fracture. Figure 2D shows fibers, which average 49 ± 13 nm in diameter, oriented parallel to the plane of fracture. Figure 2E shows a high-resolution micrograph of the mineralized fibers oriented out of the plane of the page, normal to the plane of fracture. Rotating fibers are interspersed between vertically aligned pore canal tubules, which remain in a fixed orientation normal to the surface of the dactyl club, similar to the periodic region. Arrows denote the location and orientation of these pore canal fibers. The observation of intermediate fiber angles in Figure 2C in addition to the two fiber orientations presented in Figures 2D and 2E confirm our hypothesis of a helicoidal arrangement of fibers and not simply a laminated or woven microstructure.

Figure 2. Microstructural features of the bulk impact region. (A) Low magnification SEM of fractured sagittal plane. Dashed line highlights the interface between impact and periodic regions. Scale bar, 200 μm . (B) Magnified area shown in (A) highlighting the bulk impact region. Scale bar, 50 μm . (C) Higher magnification of region denoted in (B) showing the rotated plywood structure compacted to form a herringbone pattern. Dashed lines correspond to fiber orientations transitioning between in and out of the plane of the page. Scale bar, 20 μm . (D,E) High resolution selected area micrographs from (C) showing mineralized fibers oriented in the plane of the page (D) and out of the plane of the page (E). Out of plane oriented fibers reveal underlying network of pore canal tubules, which are aligned normal to the dactyl club surface. Arrows denote pore canal fiber position and orientation. Scale bars, 2 μm .

Analysis of the impact surface region from the same fractured sample is shown in Figure 3. Figure 3A presents a low magnification overview of the impact surface interfacing with the bulk region below. The interface between the two subdomains is highlighted and shows that the impact surface is approximately 70 μm in thickness. Remnants of a herringbone-like architecture are apparent within the impact surface layer; however, moving across the interface from the bulk into the impact surface

region, we observe a gradual transition in morphology from helicoidally arranged fibers to densely packed nanoparticles. Figure 3B provides evidence of pore canal fibers, denoted by yellow arrows, extending through the impact surface region to the club surface. Higher magnification at the club surface (Figure 3C) shows densely packed nanoparticles with an average diameter of 64 ± 12 nm.

Figure 3. Microstructural features of the impact surface. (A) Low magnification SEM of fractured sagittal plane. Dashed line highlights the interface between bulk and impact surface regions. Scale bar, 20 μm . (B) Magnified area shown in (A) highlighting the particle morphology within the impact surface. Arrows denote pore canal channels that run normal to the club surface. Scale bar, 2 μm . (C) Higher magnification of region denoted in (B) showing nanoparticles averaging approximately 60 nm in diameter located at the outermost surface of the club. Scale bar, 500 nm.

2.2 Micromechanical Properties

Nanoindentation was used to probe the local and global elastic modulus and hardness of the impact region. Figure 4 shows the results of indentation mapping along the sagittal plane. Low magnification, lower resolution mapping of the impact region was performed on area B denoted in Figure 4A. Figure 4B shows the corresponding bright-field optical micrograph, which depicts the impact region interfacing with the periodic region. The area in the bottom right of Figure 4B is epoxy, the embedding material. Figures 4C and 4D shows the resulting data for elastic modulus and hardness respectively. Indents were performed in a square array with 30 μm spacing under displacement-controlled loading to 200 nm. The total indented area was 1.2 mm by 1.2 mm. The data shows that there is a sharp increase in reduced modulus and hardness transitioning from the periodic region into the impact region. Modulus and hardness then increase in a graded fashion moving through the bulk of the impact region towards the club surface. The values for reduced modulus and hardness within the bulk of the impact region range from approximately 25 to 50 GPa and 0.7 to 2 GPa respectively from the periodic region/impact region interface to just below the bulk impact region/impact surface region interface. The highest reported values for modulus and hardness occur within the impact surface region nearest to the club surface and reach approximately 60 GPa and 3 GPa respectively.

Figure 4. Nanomechanical features of the impact region. (A) Low magnification dark field optical micrograph of a polished sagittal section of the dactyl club. (B) Higher magnification bright-field optical micrograph of region denoted in (A) highlighting the impact region (IR) interfacing with the periodic region (PR). (C,D) Nanoindentation maps of region from (B) depicting local distribution of reduced Young's modulus and hardness respectively. (E) Higher magnification differential interference contrast optical micrograph of the bulk impact region denoted in (A). (F) High magnification DIC micrograph of region denoted in (E) showing the well-defined herringbone pattern within the bulk impact region. (G) High resolution nanoindentation map of region in (F) showing oscillating reduced modulus correlating with the herringbone pattern observed from optical microscopy.

High-resolution nanoindentation mapping was also conducted within the bulk of the impact region to ascertain the effect of local microstructure, namely the herringbone-like Bouligand arrangement of fibers, on the resulting modulus and hardness. Figure 4E and 4F show DIC micrographs of the polished sagittal section highlighting the herringbone pattern within the bulk of the impact region. Figure 4G shows the resulting indentation map plotting reduced modulus as a function of position. The mapped area was 90 μm by 90 μm and indents were spaced 3 μm apart in a square array. Indents were loaded in displacement control to 200 nm. The indentation map shows a strong correlation with the observed herringbone pattern from DIC imaging and SEM analyses. The reduced modulus oscillates between approximately 30 GPa and 45 GPa corresponding with the local fiber orientation within the microstructure. We hypothesize that areas of higher modulus correlate to the interrogation of fibers that are oriented out of the plane of section. Similarly, lower values of reduced modulus likely result from probing fibers that are oriented parallel to the plane of section. This is due not only to the mechanical anisotropy of the chitinous fibers, but also due to the high degree of crystallographic texturing [4]. Transmission electron microscopic analyses (data not presented here) reveal that the apatitic crystallites show a preferred orientation with c-axis aligned parallel to the fiber long axis. Additionally, Saber-Samandari and Gross examined the micromechanical properties of single crystal hydroxyapatite by nanoindentation and found that the basal planes of the single crystal exhibit higher Young's modulus as well as hardness than the side faces [5]. Thus it is expected that the oscillating modulus following the herringbone pattern within the bulk of the impact region arises due to the local fiber orientation and high degree of crystallographic texturing along the fiber long axis.

3. CONCLUSION

The results described herein confirm that the stomatopod dactyl club is highly sophisticated multi-regional composite material that has been optimized to resist failure from high energy impacting events. The impact region contains unique structural features and gradients that yield the dactyl a hard and stiff, yet tough outer surface necessary for transferring momentum to its prey while also minimizing the likelihood of fracture. These features include an amplitude graded herringbone-like Bouligand arrangement of fibers that are mineralized with a highly oriented apatitic mineral phase. The herringbone-like structure provides modulus oscillation in both the radial and azimuthal directions, which likely provides additional shielding against crack propagation over the conventional Bouligand structure (supporting data not shown here). The impact region is then terminated by a hard and stiff outer impact surface region, which is composed of densely packed and randomly oriented apatitic nanoparticles, which effectively withstand the high compressive stresses at the site of impact. The transition from particle to fibrous morphology across the bulk/impact surface interface results in a modulus mismatch that deflects cracks away from the surface. The structure-mechanical property relationships realized here will provide additional insights for the design and development of biomimetic composite materials that are exceptionally tough and impact resistant. These findings also beg the question of how such unique microstructures form in nature, which will drive future investigations of self-assembly and crystallization processes within the stomatopod dactyl club.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge financial support from the Air Force Office of Scientific Research (AFOSR-FA9550-12-1-0245) and the Air Force Office of Scientific Research, Multi-University Research Initiative (AFOSR-FA9550-15-1-0009).

REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Meyers, P.-Y. Chen, A. Y.-M. Lin, Y. Seki, Biological materials: Structure and mechanical properties. *Progress in Materials Science* **53**, 1-206 (2008).
- [2] P.-Y. Chen, J. McKittrick, M. A. Meyers, Biological materials: Functional adaptations and bioinspired designs. *Progress in Materials Science* **57**, 1492-1704 (2012).
- [3] S. N. Patek, R. L. Caldwell, Extreme impact and cavitation forces of a biological hammer: strike forces of the peacock mantis shrimp *Odontodactylus scyllarus*. *Journal of Experimental Biology* **208**, 3655-3664 (2005).
- [4] J. C. Weaver *et al.*, The stomatopod dactyl club: a formidable damage-tolerant biological hammer. *Science* **336**, 1275-1280 (2012).
- [5] S. Saber-Samandari, K. A. Gross, Micromechanical properties of single crystal hydroxyapatite by nanoindentation. *Acta Biomaterialia* **5**, 2206-2212 (2009).
- [6] Y. Bouligand, Twisted fibrous arrangements in biological materials and cholesteric mesophases. *Tissue and Cell Tissue and Cell* **4**, 189-217 (1972).
- [7] P. Romano, H. Fabritius, D. Raabe, The exoskeleton of the lobster *Homarus americanus* as an example of a smart anisotropic biological material. *Acta Biomaterialia* **3**, 301-309 (2007).
- [8] E. A. Zimmermann *et al.*, Mechanical adaptability of the Bouligand-type structure in natural dermal armour. *Nature Communications* **4**, 2634 (2013).